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Heavy Metals (HMs) Concentration in Two Sections of Ogun River, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Water is essential for the survival of all living beings, yet this precious resource faces growing threats due to the expanding human population and rising developmental activities. The study aimed to assess the heavy metals (HMs) Concentration in Two Sections of the Ogun River in Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Water samples were collected in triplicate from the two sections, then all water parameters were carried out using standard laboratory procedures. The findings indicated that both pH and temperature were elevated in the Alagada section, while electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS) were higher in the Lafenwa section of the Ogun River. Moreover, the concentrations of cadmium, copper, iron, zinc, and chromium were greater in the Alagada section, whereas manganese, nickel, and lead levels were elevated in the Lafenwa section of the river. Additionally, the concentrations of cadmium, iron, chromium, manganese, nickel, and lead in both sections, along with copper in the Alagada section, exceeded the standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO). A moderately positive correlation was also identified between copper and nickel, as well as manganese and iron, suggesting that the HMs arise from a combination of natural and human-induced sources.

Keywords: Abeokuta, Alagada, Heavy metal, Lafenwa, Ogun river

1. INTRODUCTION

Water plays a vital role in the existence of all living organisms, but this valued resource is increasingly being threatened as the human population grows and developmental activities increase (Umoren *et al.*, 2024a). Yet, the demand for good quality water for various domestic and economic activities keeps increasing. Water constitutes 70% of the total earth's surface while the other 30% is mostly present as soil moisture or is trapped in underground aquifers (Omole, 2010; Umoren *et al.*, 2024b). Ultimately, less than 1% of the world's freshwater is readily accessible for direct human use (Omole, 2010). In developing countries, where potable water supply is near rarity, most of the inhabitants rely solely on surface water. About 48% of Nigerians depend on surface water for domestic use and only 14% have access to pipe-borne water. Unfortunately, most water users are not aware of the enormity of the risk attached to unhygienic water use (Longe *et al.*, 2010; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023).

Although water plays an essential role in supporting human life and biodiversity, it also has a great potential for transmitting diseases when contaminated (Yakasai *et al.*, 2014; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025). Population growth coupled with other factors such as urbanization, agricultural activities, and industrial and commercial processes have resulted in the accumulation of wastes and pollutants which end up in water bodies, thereby altering the water quality (Dike *et al.*, 2014). Many rivers or streams particularly in developing countries are heavily polluted due to industrial and municipal wastewater discharges, as well as agricultural runoff (Li and Zhang, 2010). However, human activities are a major factor determining the quality of water resource through atmospheric pollution, effluent discharges, use of agricultural chemicals, eroded soils and land use (Oketola *et al.*, 2013).

The quality of surface water within a region is governed by natural processes such as physical, chemical and biological processes (Ayuba *et al.* 2012). Also, anthropogenic effects such as urban, industrial, and agricultural activities and the human exploitation of water resources (Noori *et al.*, 2010). Naturally, water is not pure as it acquires contaminants from its surroundings and those arising from humans, animals as well as other biological activities (Adumanya *et al.*, 2013). Water pollution is defined to be the presence of excessive amounts of a hazard (pollutants) in water in such a way that it is no longer suitable for uses (Owa, 2013).

The pollution can either be of a point source or a non-point source. A point source of pollution occurs when pollutants are emitted directly into the water body from industrial sewage or municipal wastewater pipes. A non-point source delivers pollutants indirectly through environmental changes such as pollution from urban run-off (Bangbose and Arowolo, 2007; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023).

In Nigeria, many rivers are heavily polluted with high concentrations of some HMs of variable and unsuitable physicochemical characteristics (Akinbola *et al.*, 2024). HMs have a particular significance in eco-toxicology since they are highly persistent and all have the potential to be toxic to living organisms (Izah and Angaye, 2015). HMs are non-biodegradable metallic chemical elements which have a relatively high density, toxic at low concentrations, and tend to accumulate in the sediment of waterways in association with organic and inorganic matter in the sediment.

Heavy metals include Lead (Pb), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), and Iron (Fe). The presence of these metals in the environment has been a source of worry to environmentalists, government agencies and health practitioners due to their health implications (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023).

The presence of these metals has far-reaching consequences on man and their effect include; dermal, lung and nasal cancers (Aluko *et al.*, 2024). Prolonged exposure to HMs could ultimately lead to health risks associated with the consumption of contaminated fish. Adverse effects of HMs may include serious threats like renal failure, liver damage, cardiovascular diseases and even death (Rahman *et al.*, 2012; Linnik and Zubenko, 2020).

In the Southwestern part of Nigeria, River Ogun is one of the most recognized which is used for water supply, domestic uses and agriculture. Surface water pollution is a major problem facing most developing nations. This study hereby focuses on HM concentrations of Ogun River (Alagada and Lafenwa) compared to the WHO permissible threshold.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

River Ogun is a permanent river with a total area of 22.4 km and a fairly large flow of about 393 m³/s during the wet season. The river originates from Oyo state [3° 28' E and 8° 41' N] near Shaki flows through Ogun State and discharges into the Lagos Lagoon, which is the final sink. The river Ogun water is used for agriculture, transportation, human consumption, various industrial activities and domestic purposes. The river serves as raw water for Ogun State and Lagos water works, which treat it before dispensing it to the public. Along the river basin, effluents from breweries, abattoirs, dyeing industry, and domestic wastewater are discharged (Oketola *et al.*, 2013).

The major climatic seasons are the wet season, which begins in June and ends in July and the dry season, which begins in January and ends in March. The people are mainly farmers and traders. As at the time of this research work, the study area is predominantly an urban area at Lafenwa areas (7°8'44.246''N 3°21'12.1896''E) characterized by human activities such as wood processing, agriculture, selling and buying of fish, Bathing and Religious rites., and a rural area with few industrial activities at Alagada area (7°4'23.888''N 3°20'0.6''E) characterized with human activities such as Sand mining, rearing of animals and Agriculture (Umoren *et al.*, 2024).

2. 2. Samples Collection

The sampling exercise was carried out in the month of December 2024, water samples were collected in triplicate for physiochemical parameters (pH, Temperature, Electrical Conductivity (E.C) and Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)) and HMs - Lead (Pb), Zinc (Zn), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), Copper (Cu), Iron (Fe) and Manganese (Mn) estimation. All samples were collected using pre-cleaned 2.5L plastic bottles. All plastics utilized were pre-washed with a detergent water solution, rinsed with tap water and soaked for 48 hours in 5% HNO₃, then rinsed thoroughly with distilled-deionized water. They were then air-dried in a dust-free environment.

Precautions were taken to avoid the trapping of atmospheric oxygen in the containers. Water samples for HMs were collected separately in 2.5 L capacity plastic bottles. They were preserved with 2 drops of concentrated nitric acid to prevent the absorption of HMs into the container walls. Samples were preserved in the field by keeping them in a cooler containing ice packs. They were transported to the Laboratory for subsequent analysis.

2. 3. Physical Parameters

The physical parameters of the samples were determined according to the standard method. This includes Temperature (°C), pH, Electrical Conductivity (µS/cm) and Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L). They were carried out in situ using a pocket-size water quality meter. The probe was rinsed with distilled water before use in each case and allowed to stay in the sample till the timer was stabilized for reading. The meter displays the value of pH and temperature first, then when the mode button is pressed its value for electrical conductivity and total dissolved solids shows on the screen.

2. 4. Acid Digestion and HM Extraction

Exactly 50 mL of the water sample was digested with 10 ml of nitric acid for two hours on the digestion block. The nitric acid was added to mineralize the solution. The sample was set on a hot plate at 150 °C until the volume was reduced to 20 mL. After digestion, it was allowed to cool and made up to 50 mL with distilled water in a 50 mL volumetric flask. The HMs were read using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Buck Scientific, Model 211).

2. 5. Statistical Analysis

Data collected were analyzed for descriptive statistics. Analysis of variance (one-way) and correlation analysis using the SPSS for Windows version 20.0 was also employed to interpret the similarities and differences among the HMs.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Results

3. 1. 1. Physical Parameters of Water

The results for the physical parameters of the water samples in the Alagada and Lafenwa sections of Ogun River are shown in Table 1. The pH values ranged between sections with the higher pH value recorded in Alagada (6.79±0.33) and the lower pH in Lafenwa (6.77±0.41). The pH values were within the WHO standard (6.5 - 8.5). The temperature values ranged between sections with the higher temperature recorded in Alagada (26.78±1.10 °C) and the lower temperature in Lafenwa (26.47±1.05 °C). The temperature values were within the WHO standard (25.5 - 29.0 °C).

Table 1. Some Physical parameters of the samples.

Parameters	Alagbada	Lafenwa	WHO (2011)
pH	6.79±0.33	6.77±0.41	6.5- 8.5
Temp. (°C)	26.78±1.10	26.47±1.05	25.5 - 29.0
EC (µS/cm)	13.84±4.67	47.21±32.86	1000
TDS (mg/ L)	72.09±2.70	72.81±5.27	500

The electrical conductivity (EC) values ranged between sections with the higher electrical conductivity value recorded in Lafenwa ($47.21 \pm 32.86 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) while the lower electrical conductivity in Alagada ($13.84 \pm 4.67 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). The electrical conductivity values were within the WHO standard ($1000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$). The total dissolved solids (TDS) values ranged between sections with the higher total dissolved solids value recorded in Lafenwa ($72.81 \pm 5.27 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) while the lower total dissolved solids in Alagada ($72.09 \pm 2.70 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The total dissolved solids values were within the WHO standard ($500 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$).

3. 1. 2. HMs Concentration

The results for the HMs in water samples in the Alagada and Lafenwa sections of Ogun River are shown in Table 2. The Cadmium concentration was higher in Alagada ($0.48 \pm 0.35 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Lafenwa ($0.30 \pm 0.24 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Cd concentration between the sections was not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Cd concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.003 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Cu concentration was higher in Alagada ($3.36 \pm 2.28 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Lafenwa ($1.71 \pm 1.91 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Cu concentrations between the sections were significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, only the Cu concentration in the Alagada section was above the WHO standard ($2.00 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Fe concentration was higher in Alagada ($1.87 \pm 2.52 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Lafenwa ($1.19 \pm 0.64 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Fe concentration between the sections was not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Fe concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.3 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$).

The Mn concentration was higher in Lafenwa ($19.66 \pm 11.94 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Alagada ($3.55 \pm 2.88 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Mn concentration between the sections was significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Mn concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.05 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Ni concentration was higher in Lafenwa ($1.85 \pm 0.85 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Alagada ($1.77 \pm 0.72 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Ni concentration between the sections was not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Ni concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.02 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Pb concentration was higher in Lafenwa ($0.61 \pm 0.06 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Alagada ($0.26 \pm 0.35 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Pb concentration between the sections was not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Pb concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.01 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$).

The Zn concentration was higher in Alagada ($0.66 \pm 0.84 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) while the lower level was in Lafenwa ($0.55 \pm 0.49 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Zn concentration between the sections was not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Zn concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($3.00 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Cr concentration was higher in Alagada ($0.50 \pm 0.12 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and lower in Lafenwa ($0.22 \pm 0.13 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$). The Cr concentration between the sections was significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the Cr concentration in the sections was above the WHO standard ($0.05 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$).

Table 2. HMs concentration.

HMs (mg/L)	Alagbada	Lafenwa	WHO (2011)
Cadmium	$0.48^a \pm 0.35$	$0.30^a \pm 0.24$	0.003
Copper	$3.36^a \pm 2.28$	$1.71^b \pm 1.91$	2.00

Iron	1.87 ^a ±2.52	1.19 ^a ±0.64	0.3
Manganese	3.55 ^a ±2.88	19.6 ^b ±11.94	0.05
Nickel	1.77 ^a ±0.72	1.85 ^a ±0.85	0.02
Lead	0.26 ^a ±0.35	0.61 ^a ±0.06	0.01
Zinc	0.66 ^a ±0.84	0.55 ^a ±0.49	3.00
Chromium	0.50 ^{ab} ±0.12	0.22 ^a ±0.13	0.05

- Mean values with the different superscripts across rows are significantly different at p<0.05
 - Values in bold are higher than the WHO standards

3. 1. 3. Correlation Between HMs

Correlation between metals can give good information about their sources and routes in the environment (Akinbola *et al.*, 2024). Pearson's correlation estimated between metals is presented in Table 3. Reveals that Cu was significantly related to Ni ($r = 0.584$), $p < 0.05$) while Mn was significantly related to Fe ($r = 0.505$, $p < 0.05$). The significantly related HMs indicate similarities in source of origin. The moderately positive relationship between Cu and Ni; and Mn and Fe shows that the metals are mixed of natural and anthropogenic sources.

Table 3. Correlation Matrix.

	Cu	Zn	Fe	Ni	Pb	Mn	Cd	Cr
Cu	1							
Zn	-0.033	1						
Fe	0.081	0.353	1					
Ni	0.584*	-0.136	0.183	1				
Pb	0.021	-0.323	-0.269	-0.008	1			
Mn	-0.111	0.418	0.505*	0.020	-0.314	1		
Cd	0.290	0.066	-0.008	-0.018	-0.119	0.274	1	
Cr	-0.233	-0.203	-0.459	-0.487	0.133	-0.573	-0.132	1

Values in bold are moderately positive ($p < 0.05$)

3. 2. Discussion

The quality of water is neither a static state of an ecosystem nor the measurement of various parameters. The physical and chemical variables provide a general pointing of water pollution while the HMs provide a direct tracking of the pollution sources (Kolawole *et al.*, 2011). The pH is one of the most important water parameters as most of the aquatic ecosystems are adapted to an average pH of 7.00, above 7.00 is regarded as an alkaline condition while below 7.00 is regarded as an acidic condition. The pH obtained in the two sections was weakly acidic which could be attributed to the increase in respiration from biota which leads to the release of CO₂ in the water body thereby increasing the production of carbonic acid and hydroxyl ions, which in turn increases acidity. The result obtained in this study agreed with the findings of Kolawole *et al.*, (2011) who reported the slightly acidic pH in Asa River, Kwara State, Nigeria (6.20 - 6.43).

Temperature is another important water quality parameter that indicates the level of pollution in water bodies. Water temperature observed throughout the study period, however, falls within the WHO standard (25.5 - 29.0 °C). The difference in water temperature could be attributed to high humidity and an increase in rainfall to cool the atmospheric temperature of the environment. The surface water temperature observed in this study agreed with the findings of Ojekunle *et al.* (2014) who reported a water temperature range of 24.3 – 27.5 °C in Ogun River but contrary to the trend observed by Oketola *et al.*, (2013) who reported the temperature range of river Ogun (28 – 32 °C).

Electrical conductivity (EC) is another important parameter in water quality assessment, as it measures the level of anions and cations in water bodies. The electrical conductivity values recorded in the sections are similar to those of Alani *et al.* (2014). The low EC value is very good as high conductivity may reduce the quality of the water by giving the miner a taste of the water in line with (Kavcar *et al.*, 2019). Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) is the measure of the sum of all organic and inorganic substances in a liquid (Abir, 2014), in molecular, ionized or micro-granular colloidal suspended form (IC, 2014).

TDS concentration in a water body is affected by many different factors. TDS values will change when ions are introduced to water from salts, acid bases, hard water minerals or soluble gases that ionize in solution. The TDS observed in this study complies with the WHO standard and is lower than the report from Iju River, Ogun state, Nigeria (96-153 mg/L) by Famuyiwa *et al.* (2023) but slightly higher than that of Uren River, Ogun state, Nigeria (58.33 - 60.33 mg/L) by Akinbola *et al.* (2025). The low level of TDS observed shows good quality. Golterman (2018) asserted that water with high TDS is generally of inferior palatability and may induce an unfavourable physiological reaction.

The presence of the recorded HMs may be attributed to discharge from agricultural wastes, sand mining, oil spillage, wood processing, refuse disposal, and domestic waste from the catchment areas. Cadmium toxicity from the two sections can result in health issues such as respiratory and kidney dysfunctions on prolonged exposure (WHO 2011; Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023). The result from the study was higher than Cd reported in Osun stream (0.03 mg/l), Nigeria (Adebanjo and Adedeji, 2019) and Iju River (0.004 -0.005 mg/L), Ogun state Nigeria (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2023).

The concentration of copper in the study is higher than that of the Omu–Aran (1.21- 1.08 mg/L), Nigeria (Elemile *et al.*, 2019) and Stream in Abeokuta (0.00025 mg/L), Nigeria (Osifeso *et al.*, 2025). The high level of Cu in the Alagada sample can be linked the human activities around the water bodies. Copper toxicity in water can result in health issues such as headaches,

vomiting, diarrhoea, stomach cramps, nausea, liver damage, and kidney disease (Bui et al., 2016).

Iron in water promotes the development of iron-reducing bacteria that help with the oxidation process that transforms iron II into iron III (WHO 2011). The concentration of Fe in the sections is high, Although, Fe does not pose a health hazard but results in the unpalatable taste of the water (WHO 2011). The concentration of Mn in the samples is high, a prolonged ingestion of Mn has been reported to result in a decline in brain cells of the Nervous system (Tenge *et al.*, 2015). Manganese recorded in this study was higher than what was observed in a river (0.34mg/L) by Davies & Ekperusi (2021) and a stream in Abeokuta (0.003 mg/L), Nigeria (Osifeso *et al.*, 2025).

Lead is described to be a potentially hazardous metal to various forms of life by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2014). The concentration of Pb from the study is higher than the reports from Minna, Niger State, Nigeria (0.01 - 0.09 mg/L) (Idris *et al.*, 2013) and Omu – Aran, Nigeria (0.06 -0.16 mg/L) (Elemile *et al.*, 2019). Nickel is well known trace element enormously distributed in the environment, being a metal released from the combination of lithogenic sources and man-made activity, with a great input from the combination of both the stationary and the mobile sources. Nickel concentration for the study was higher than the report from the stream, Abeokuta (0.0018 mg/L), Nigeria (Osifeso *et al.*, 2025) and another stream, Abeokuta (0.003 mg/L), Nigeria (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025).

High Zn concentration in water causes an unpalatable taste at a level >4 mg/l, more so, causing opalescent and developing scums when boiled at a level > 3-5 mg/l (WHO, 2011). No health implication however has been attributed to Zinc in water (Aluko *et al.*, 2024). The Zn level recorded in the study complies with the regulatory authorities. Chromium is considered a low-moving toxic metal, most especially under moderately redox conditions and at nearly neutral pH.

The principal source of Chromium is industrial steel while other sources are amalgams, chrome coating, and colour production (Aluko *et al.*, 2024; Osifeso *et al.*, 2025).

The concentration of Chromium recovered in the study was higher than the report from a stream in Abeokuta (0.007), Nigeria (Famuyiwa *et al.*, 2025) and another stream in Abeokuta (0.0020 mg/l), Nigeria (Osifeso *et al.*, 2025).

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

4. 1. Conclusion

The present study was carried out on the Alagada and Lafenwa sections of the Ogun River. The study investigates some physical parameters (pH, temperature, electrical conductivity and total dissolved solids) and HM (lead, cadmium, chromium, zinc, nickel, copper iron, manganese) concentration between the study areas. The study revealed that the pH and Temperature were higher in the Alagada section while EC and TDS were Lafenwa section of the Ogun River.

Furthermore, the levels of Cd, Cu, Fe, Zn and Cr were higher in the Alagada section while Mn, Ni and Pb were higher in the Lafenwa section of the Ogun River. Additionally, the levels of Cd, Fe, Cr, Mn, Ni and Pb in the two sections, and Cu in the Alagada section were above the WHO standard. A moderately positive relationship between Cu and Ni; Mn and Fe was also observed indicating that the metals are mixed of natural and anthropogenic sources.

4. 2. Recommendation

It is recommended that:

- 1) A regular assessment of the river water quality is suggested to ensure the water quality is safe for public health.
- 2) Public sensitization of the risk associated with indiscriminate waste disposal as well as evolving measures to control pollution is encouraged.
- 3) Ogun River should be protected through conscious planning and reorganization of activities along the river.

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